

BiolmagingUK & UK Physics of Life Network

Equality, diversity and inclusion survey

Consent and Terms

The Equal Group has partnered with BiolmagingUK & UK Physics of Life Network to facilitate an anonymous EDI survey.

All data is collected in a confidential manner, no uniquely identifiable information will be shared at any time. We will not transfer your personal data to any third party, unless otherwise required by law or authorised by you. We will keep your data for as long as necessary in relation to our agreement with BiolmagingUK & UK Physics of Life Network. You are responsible for the veracity of the data you share with The Equal Group.

Regarding your data, you have the right to:

- Obtain access to the personal data held about you in our files (right of access)
- Ask for your personal data to be corrected (right of rectification)
- Request the restriction of the processing of your personal data (right to restriction of processing)
- Have your personal data deleted (right to erasure)
- Limit the processing of your personal data under permitted circumstances (right to limitation of processing)
- Receive in a machine-readable format your personal data and any other data obtained during your relationship with The Equal Group and send it to another controller ('data portability')

You can exercise the aforementioned rights at the following e-mail address: contact@theequalgroup.com

Demographics

Membership

Are you currently a member of BiolmagingUK & UK Physics of Life Network (i.e. are you on either mailing list):

- Yes - BiolmagingUK

- Yes – UK Physics of Life Network
- Yes – Both
- Unsure
- No
 - If no, why not:
 - Not interested
 - Unfamiliar with the mailing list
 - Too many emails already
 - Privacy concerns
 - Prefer other ways to stay updated
 - Other [free text]

How long have you been a member of the relevant network(s)?

- Less than 12 months
- 1-2 years
- 2-3 years
- 4+ years
- Unsure
- Prefer not to say

Where are you primarily based?

- England
- Scotland
- Northern Ireland
- Wales
- Republic of Ireland
- International
 - If international, please provide details

What type of institution do you currently work for?

- Academic Institution
 - If so, which [Free text]
- Industry
- Charity sector
- Policy/government
- Other Research Institution
- Other: Self-describe

**Which of these options best describes the level of your position at the organisation?
[Where more than one applies please consider your main role]**

- Senior – established or leading scientist, core facility lead/deputy

- Mid-level – PhD holder or equivalent, not fully independent, core facility staff, technician
- Early – Student (e.g. Undergraduate, Masters or PhD student), core facility staff, technician
- Retired (no longer working)
- Other: Self-Describe

Age

What is your age?

- Under 18
- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65+
- Prefer not to say

Gender

What gender do you identify as?

- Man
- Non-Binary / Genderqueer
- Woman
- Prefer to Self-Describe: [free text]
- Prefer not to say

Ethnicity

How would you describe your ethnicity? [Please choose one option that best describes your ethnic group or background]

- Asian or Asian British
 - Bangladeshi
 - Chinese
 - Indian
 - Pakistani
 - Any other Asian background
- Black, African, Caribbean or Black British
 - African
 - Caribbean
 - Any other Black, African or Caribbean background
- Mixed or Multiple ethnic groups

- White and Black Caribbean
- White and Black African
- White and Asian
- Any other Mixed or Multiple ethnic background
- White or White British
 - English, Welsh, Scottish, Northern Irish or British
 - Irish
 - Gypsy or Irish Traveller
 - Any other White background
- Other ethnic group
 - Arab
 - Any other ethnic group
- Prefer to Self-Describe: [free text]
- Prefer not to say

Disability

Please note, responding to this survey, and these two questions in particular will not be considered a formal disclosure of any disability, long-term health condition, or neurodiversity to BioImagingUK & UK Physics of Life Network.

Do you consider yourself to have any of the following disabilities or long-term health conditions?

- Yes
 - A condition affecting motor, cognitive, emotional, speech, language, communication or social skills
 - Hearing impairment or deafness
 - Long-term illness (for example, cancer, HIV, diabetes, chronic heart disease or epilepsy)
 - Mental health condition (for example, depression, anxiety disorder, schizophrenia)
 - Physical disability or mobility issue (for example, impaired use of limbs, or use of a wheelchair or mobility aid)
 - Visual impairment not corrected by glasses or blindness
 - Another disability, health condition, or impairment affecting daily life
- No
- Prefer to Self-Describe: [free text]
- Prefer not to say

Do you consider yourself to have a neurodiverse condition (diagnosed or undiagnosed)? [Tick all that apply]

- Yes – Autism
- Yes – ADHD

- Yes – Dyslexia
- Yes – Dyspraxia
- Yes – Other – Self describe: [free text]
- No
- I don't know
- Prefer not to say

Caring responsibility

Are you a parent/guardian or caregiver of one or more dependents (e.g. children under 18, adults with health conditions or disability, or those with drug/alcohol dependency)? [Tick all that apply]

- Yes – Parent
- Yes – Parent of child(ren) with special needs
- Yes – Carer for one or more adult(s)
- No
- Prefer not to say

Educational Background

This section includes some questions in relation to your education and that of your parents, to consider social mobility across generations.

What is the highest level of education you have completed? [If you are currently studying, please select the highest level obtained]

- Doctorate
- Masters
- Undergraduate Degree
- Diploma
- Professional Qualification
- Other – Self describe: [free text]
- Prefer not to say

What best describes the majority of your secondary school education?

- Home schooling
- A state-run or state-funded school
- Independent or fee-paying school
- Independent or fee-paying school, where I received a bursary covering 90% or more of my tuition
- Attended school outside the UK
- Unknown
- Other – Self describe: [free text]
- Prefer not to say

**What is the highest level of education your parent(s) / guardian(s) have completed?
[Where there may be a disparity – please select the highest achieved qualification]**

- Doctorate
- Masters
- Undergraduate Degree
- Diploma
- Professional Qualification
- Secondary / High School
- Primary / Elemental
- Unknown
- Other – Self describe: [free text]
- Prefer not to say

What was the occupation of your main household earner when you were aged 14?

- Professional (e.g., doctor, lawyer, engineer, teacher)
- Managerial (e.g., manager, supervisor, executive)
- Skilled (e.g., electrician, plumber, technician, craftsman)
- Semi-skilled (e.g., factory worker, sales assistant, driver)
- Semi-routine and routine (e.g., labourer, cleaner)
- Unemployed?
- Other – Self describe: [free text]
- Prefer not to say

If you finished school after 1980, were you eligible for free school meals at any point during your school years?

- Yes
- No
- Not applicable (finished school before 1980 or went to school overseas)
- I do not know / unsure
- Prefer not to say

Qualitative Questions

Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the following statements.

I feel like I belong within the BiolmagingUK & UK Physics of Life Network:

- Strongly Agree

- Agree
- Neither agree, nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

BiolmagingUK & UK Physics of Life Network actively promotes fair treatment of all members regardless of their different diversity characteristics:

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neither agree, nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

BiolmagingUK & UK Physics of Life Network provides me with the support (including training, safe spaces, mentoring etc.) I need to engage with people from all backgrounds and experiences:

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neither agree, nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

I feel comfortable talking about equality, diversity and inclusion within Biolmaging UK & UK Physics of Life Network:

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neither agree, nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

I feel empowered to make positive contributions to BiolmagingUK & UK Physics of Life Network:

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neither agree, nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

Free text questions

We would appreciate you answering the following free text questions as they will allow us to draw a greater insight into your experiences. These questions can be answered in bullet point form if easier.

Are there any barriers or difficulties you have experienced related to equality, diversity or inclusivity when engaging with Biology and/or Physics research in general? [Please provide details]

- Free text

Thinking about all the BioImagingUK & UK Physics of Life Network's activities (including in-person and online meetings, communications and funding schemes) in terms of equality, diversity and inclusion, what do BioImagingUK & UK Physics of Life Network currently do well?

- Free text

Thinking about those same activities in terms of equality, diversity and inclusion, what could the BioImagingUK & UK Physics of Life Networks do better?

- Free text

What equality, diversity inclusion initiatives / activities should the BioImagingUK & UK Physics of Life Networks focus on during the next 12 months?

- Free text

Do you have any other comments about any equality, diversity and inclusion aspects you have not yet been asked about or would like to share more detail about?

- Free text